

A comparative study of crystalline state properties of alkali halides using the three standard potential models

J. Mandal* and B. Ghatak

University Department of Physics, T. M. Bhagalpur University, Bhagalpur-812 007, Bihar, India

Manuscript received 15 January 2007, revised 1 June 2007, accepted 11 July 2007

Abstract : Interionic short-range repulsive potential models due to Born-Mayer, Hellmann and Ali-Hasan have been used to estimate the crystalline state properties such as cohesive energy, atomization energy, Grüneisen parameter, Andersen-Grüneisen parameter, Moelwyn-Hughes parameter and first order volume dependence of Grüneisen parameter commonly known as second order Grüneisen parameter of alkali halides of NaCl structure.

Keywords : Standard potential, alkali halide, crystalline state.

A number of short range repulsive potential functions that have been proposed by different authors are in capable of explaining all properties of diatomic ionic crystals¹. In the present study we have used the three standard forms of short range repulsive potentials due to Born-Mayer, Hellmann and Ali-Hasan to predict the various crystalline state properties of alkali halides². These models take into account the contributions arising from Van der Waals dipole-dipole (Vdw) and dipole-quadrupole interactions to crystalline state properties.

The lattice energy per ion pair of a diatomic crystal can be written as

$$W(r) = -AZ^2e^2/r - C/r^6 - D/r^8 + W_{sr}(r) \quad (1)$$

The first term of the right-hand side of the above equation is the long-range electrostatic Coulomb energy with Madelung constant A . Ze is the electronic charge on the ions. r is the equilibrium interionic distance. The second and the third terms are Van der Waals dipole-dipole (Vdw) and dipole-quadrupole interactions respectively. Values of Vdw constants C and D have been taken from literature³. The fourth term $W_{sr}(r)$ is the short-range repulsive potential (SRRP) which is dominant in diatomic ionic crystals. It is related to the overlap integrals through the concept of exchange charge interactions. The SRRP perturbs the spherically symmetric closed shell of an ion in a lattice. As the ions are brought closer together so that outer electron shells begin to overlap an additional characteristic repulsive force becomes operative resulting from overlapping of the ions. This repulsive force opposes the Coulomb attractive force operating between positive and negative ions and causes them to come to equilibrium at finite value of the interionic distance. The repulsive force

in an ion becomes dominant at a very short distance so it is known as Short-Range Repulsive Potential. The potential parameters S_1 , ρ and b appearing in $W_{sr}(r)$ have been calculated by using the usual crystal stability and compressibility conditions⁴.

The atomization energies of the ionic crystals may be calculated from the interaction potential function using the simple relation.

$$E_a = W + E - I \quad (2)$$

where E is the electron affinity and I is the ionization energy. Values of E have been taken from literature⁵. Calculated values of cohesive energies and atomization energies based on the three potential models have been listed in Table 1 along with the experimental values.

The Grüneisen parameter (γ) can be expressed as

$$\gamma = -r_0/6 W'''(r_0)/W''(r_0) \quad (3)$$

where $W''(r)$ and $W'''(r)$ refer to the second and third derivatives of $W(r)$.

The Anderson-Grüneisen parameter (δ) have been computed using Chang's relation connecting γ and δ derived on the basis of Dugdale and Macdonald relationship between Grüneisen parameter (γ) and change of compressibility with volumes.

The values of Moelwyn-Hughes parameter C_1 have been calculated for the three potentials using the relation⁷

$$C_1 = 1 - \beta/27K_1 W'''(r_0) \quad (4)$$

where β is the compressibility and K_1 is the crystal structure having the values 2 and 1.54 for NaCl and CsCl-structures respectively.

Note

Table 1

Name of crystal	Cohesive energy in kcal mol ⁻¹				Atomisation energy in kcal mol ⁻¹			
	BM	Hell	AH	Expt. value ¹⁰	BM	Hell	AH	Expt. value ¹¹
LiF	247.9	246.9	248.4	247.7	206.8	200.8	202.3	203
LiCl	199.0	198.3	199.6	203.2	159.1	158.4	159.7	165
LiBr	187.5	186.8	188.1	194.2	132.8	133.1	134.4	151
LiI	173.2	172.6	173.9	180.3	122.9	122.3	123.6	121
NaF	221.0	220.4	221.7	219.5	180.7	180.1	181.4	180
NaCl	184.6	184.1	185.2	187.1	150.5	150.0	151.1	153
NaBr	175.4	174.9	176.0	178.5	127.0	127.5	128.1	135
NaI	163.6	163.1	164.3	167.0	119.1	118.6	119.8	113
KF	195.4	194.9	196.1	194.3	173.5	173.0	174.2	174
KCl	168.7	168.2	169.3	170.2	153.0	152.5	153.6	155
KBr	161.5	161.0	162.1	163.2	132.0	131.5	132.6	134
KI	152.1	151.7	152.7	153.6	126.0	125.6	126.6	118
RbF	187.3	186.8	187.9	185.8	169.2	168.7	169.8	170
RbCl	162.9	162.5	163.5	163.6	151.0	150.6	151.6	152
RbBr	156.2	155.8	156.8	157.2	130.5	130.1	131.1	137
RbI	143.3	146.0	146.9	148.5	121.0	123.7	124.6	117
CsF	179.0	178.6	179.6	177.0	167.4	167.0	168.0	164
CsCl	156.4	156.0	157.0	159.8	151.0	150.6	151.6	151
CsBr	151.7	151.3	152.4	154.1	132.5	132.1	133.2	136
CsI	143.6	143.2	144.2	146.1	127.8	127.4	128.0	117

Table 2

Name of crystal	Moelwyn-Hughes parameter				Grüneisen parameter				Anderson-Grüneisen parameter			
	BM	Hell	AH	Expt. value ¹²	BM	Hell	AH	Expt. value ¹³	BM	Hell	AH	Expt. value ¹⁴
LiF	3.75	3.86	3.74		1.38	1.42	1.37	1.63	2.75	2.85	2.74	3.56
LiCl	4.0	4.09	3.95		1.50	1.54	1.47	1.81	3.00	3.09	2.95	4.09
LiBr	4.04	4.14	3.99		1.52	1.57	1.49	1.94	3.04	3.14	2.98	4.12
LiI	4.07	4.17	4.01		1.53	1.58	1.50	2.19	3.07	3.17	3.01	4.06
NaF	4.12	4.20	4.07	8.29	1.56	1.69	1.53	1.51	3.12	3.38	3.07	3.75
NaCl	4.29	4.38	4.23	5.77	1.65	1.69	1.61	1.61	3.29	3.38	3.23	3.80
NaBr	4.34	4.42	4.26		1.67	1.71	1.63	1.64	3.34	3.42	3.26	4.11
NaI	4.40	4.49	4.32		1.70	1.74	1.6	1.71	3.40	3.49	3.32	4.13
KF	4.36	4.44	4.29		1.68	1.72	1.64	1.52	3.36	3.44	3.29	4.08
KCl	4.51	4.60	4.43	4.83	1.76	1.80	1.71	1.49	3.51	3.60	3.43	4.38
KBr	4.52	4.61	4.44		1.76	1.80	1.72	1.50	3.52	3.61	3.44	4.02
KI	4.57	4.65	4.47		1.78	1.83	1.73	1.53	3.57	3.66	3.47	3.93
RbF	4.57	4.64	4.48		1.78	1.82	1.74	1.40	3.57	3.65	3.48	4.97
RbCl	4.66	4.74	4.57	4.53	1.83	1.87	1.78	1.39	3.66	3.74	3.57	4.93
RbBr	4.67	4.75	4.57		1.83	1.87	1.78	1.42	3.67	3.75	3.57	4.72
RbI	4.77	4.85	4.67		1.88	1.92	1.83	1.56	3.77	3.84	3.67	4.47
CsF	4.75	4.83	4.65		1.87	1.91	1.82		3.75	3.83	3.65	
CsCl	4.97	5.04	4.85		1.98	2.02	1.92		3.97	4.04	3.85	
CsBr	4.97	5.06	4.86		1.99	2.03	1.93		3.97	4.06	3.86	
CsI	5.02	5.10	4.90		2.01	2.05	1.95		4.02	4.10	3.90	

The first order volume dependence of the Grüneisen parameter is known as the second Grüneisen parameter. It is an additional measure of the anharmonicity in solids. Using thermodynamic relations⁸ derived the following expressions for

$$q = \gamma (1 + 2\gamma \alpha_v T) \quad (5)$$

where the values of α_v , volume coefficient of thermal expansion⁹ and T is absolute temperature.

Results and discussion

In the present study it is observed that the values of cohesive energies and atomisation energies based on the Hellmann potential are only slightly better than those obtained from BM potential. The values obtained from AH potential are in close agreement with the experimental values.

The Grüneisen parameter (γ), Anderson-Grüneisen parameter (δ) and Moelwyn-Hughes parameter (C_1) calculated on the basis of the three models are listed in Table 2. It is observed that the Born-Mayer and Hellmann potentials give results of these parameters in close agreement with their experimental values.

Acknowledgement

We are extremely thankful to Prof. Md. M. Hasan for his constant encouragement and valuable suggestions and the University Department of Physics, T. M. Bhagalpur University, Bhagalpur. We duly recognise the valuable suggestions made by the honourable referee.

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